

Separation and preconcentration of rare earth elements in geological materials using used tea leaves and their determination by ICP-OES

D. P. S. Rathore

Former Senior Scientist, Atomic Minerals Directorate for Exploration & Research,
Department of Atomic Energy, Jaipur-302 033, Rajasthan, India

E-mail : dpsr2002@yahoo.com

Manuscript received online 20 August 2015, accepted 22 August 2016

Abstract : As claimed by the authors, quote “A simple method has been developed for the separation and preconcentration of Rare Earth Elements (REEs) in different types of geological materials using the sorption property of the used green tea leaves (UGTL’s)” unquote. This manuscript is lacking in basic fundamental studies related with sorption properties of UGTL towards individual REEs, such as, source of UGTL, characterization of UGTL, equilibrium isotherm models, biosorption kinetics and thermodynamics, FTIR and SEM analysis of loaded and unloaded biosorbent, etc., prior to its quantitative application in REEs separation and preconcentration studies followed by ICP-OES measurement. Authors claim is absolutely wrong and highly misleading. Relevant and up-to-date citations to published literature on tea leaves as biosorbent are missing. What is the purpose of citing irrelevant references in the text of the manuscript by simply copying and pasting all references cited in their previous publication on UGTL by Vijay Kumar, Satya Prakash and P. N. Bangroo, titled “Synthesis of immobilized used green tea leaves on silica gel and its application in separation/preconcentration of uranium and trace elements in hydrogeochemical samples” in the journal “Exploration and Research for Atomic Minerals”, Vol. 19, pp. 97-101, year, 2009 (© Director, AMD, DAE, Govt. of India, ISSN-0970-9231), of course without citing this relevant publication. It clearly reflects the quality of their earlier publication too and claims are unsubstantiated.

Keywords : Separation, rare-earth elements, used green tea leaves, sodium fluoride, ICP-OES.

I have read the above cited paper¹, all the cited papers in references and available published literature on the above subject very carefully. Undersigned has been involved in the analysis of geological materials and hydro-geochemical reconnaissance surveys attached with mobile geochemical laboratories in different parts of India for exploration activities of Atomic Minerals Directorate for Exploration and Research.

This cited manuscript¹ is lacking in basic fundamental studies related with sorption properties of UGTL towards individual REEs and on update of recent literature published on low cost adsorbents. There are excellent reviews published in the literature on ‘Biosorption of Heavy Metals – An Overview’ by Das *et al.*², a review by Geetha and Belagali³ on ‘Removal of Heavy Metals and Dyes Using Low Cost Adsorbents from Aqueous Medium – A

Review’, a review by Das and Das⁴ on ‘Recovery of Rare Earth Metals through Biosorption : An Overview’. These review articles provide an overview of past achievements and current scenario of the biosorption studies carried out using some promising biosorbents which could serve as an economical means for recovering from wastes/removal of dyes, heavy metals, rare earth metals. The experimental findings reported by different workers will provide insights into this research frontier.

Biosorption is one of the emerging biological methods having several advantages over the conventional methods. This process does not produce any chemical sludge, easy to operate and very efficient for the removal of pollutants from very dilute solutions. A major advantage is that it can be used *in situ* and with proper design. It may not need any industrial process operations and can be

*For correspondence : 150/8, Shiprapath, Mansarovar, Jaipur-302 020, Rajasthan, India.

integrated with many systems⁵. The initial incentives for biosorption development in industrial process are the low cost of biosorbents, their high efficiency for metal removal (especially in low-concentration solutions), the biosorbent regeneration (and the potential metal recovery), the fast kinetics of adsorption and desorption, and the non-generation of secondary residues⁶. Rare earth metals (REMs) are a series of 17 elements. Biosorption studies of various rare earth metals namely, La, Nd, Ce, Er, Yb, Eu, Sm and Dy using different adsorbents in batch mode have been reported as summarized in the review⁴. Some of the papers on removal of heavy metals (cobalt, cadmium, and zinc) from waste water using black tea waste⁷, sorption/removal of lead by spent tea leaf^{8,9}, adsorption of lead(II) on spent tea leaves of green and black tea¹⁰ and removal of copper(II) from aqueous solution using spent tea leaves as a potential sorbent¹¹ are interesting.

As reported in the literature, the adsorption capacity is an important factor, because it determines how much sorbent is required to quantitatively concentrate the analytes from a given solution. From the available literature¹², there is a decrease in adsorption of uranium on AC in the presence of fluoride, nitrate, thiosulphate and oxalate ions can be attributed to weak adsorption of the anionic complexes. Qadeer *et al.*¹³ published their studies on surface characterization and thermodynamics of adsorption of Sr^{2+} , Ce^{3+} , Sm^{3+} , Gd^{3+} , Th^{4+} , UO_2^{2+} on activated charcoal from aqueous solution. As reported by the authors⁷, on page 130, Table 4.9, quote "To check the selectivity of activated charcoal for gadolinium, the adsorption of U, Er, Dy, Sm, Ce, La, Ba, Cs, Cd, Y, Sr, Rb, Zn, Cu, Co, Mn, Cr and V on activated charcoal was examined at optimum conditions for gadolinium. The results indicate that Dy, Sm, Eu, Er, U, La, Y, Ce and Ba have considerably higher values of distribution coefficient (K_D). So they would coadsorb along with gadolinium on activated charcoal. Cr, Cd, Cs, Co, Ni, Zn, Mn, V, Sr, Cu and Rb have small K_D values, hence they are poorly adsorbs on activated charcoal" unquote. The K_D values are different for each rare earth element. Therefore, separation and preconcentration of REEs using activated charcoal system is practically impossible. Similarly, these parameters need to be studied for UGTL's system in the presence of heavy metals and other associated ma-

nor, minor and trace elements in different geological matrices. A range of major, minor and trace element including REEs should be given for ensuring the applicability of the proposed method for different geological matrices.

Moreover, in view of the solubility products values of REEs fluorides¹⁴ and the conditions used by the authors (0.12 M NaF medium, pH ~ 3) for adsorption of REEs on UGTL's needs further investigations on the role of UGTL's. In my opinion, this manuscript is lacking in basic fundamental studies related with sorption properties of UGTL's towards individual REEs, such as, source of UGTL's, characterization of UGTL's, equilibrium isotherm models (K_D values), biosorption kinetics, thermodynamic parameters for adsorption, the behaviour of individual rare earths, adsorption of REEs as a function of their concentration, adsorption of REEs in the presence of different cations namely, sodium, potassium, cobalt, zinc, chromium, copper, nickel, barium, strontium, lead, cadmium, manganese, thorium, vanadium; adsorption in presence of different anions, FTIR and SEM analysis of loaded and unloaded biosorbent, etc., prior to its quantitative application in REEs separation and preconcentration studies followed by ICP-OES measurement. In view of the concern expressed as above, Authors claim is absolutely wrong and highly misleading.

In addition to, relevant and up-to-date citations of references/support to the stated statements to the published literature on tea leaves as biosorbent are missing. What is the purpose of citing irrelevant references in the text of the manuscript by simply copying and pasting all references cited in their previous publication¹⁵ on UGTL's by Vijay Kumar, Satya Prakash and P. N. Bangroo, titled "Synthesis of immobilized used green tea leaves on silica gel and its application in separation/preconcentration of uranium and trace elements in hydrogeochemical samples" published in the journal "Exploration and Research for Atomic Minerals, Vol. 19, pp. 97-101, year, 2009 (© Director, AMD, DAE, Govt. of India, ISSN-0970-9231), of course without citing this relevant publication.

About references 1-4 cited in the manuscript : Reference No. 1 titled 'Determination of ten rare-earth elements and yttrium in silicate rocks by ICP-AES without separation and preconcentration', 2nd Ref. is on 'Rare earth element geochemistry', 3rd Ref. titled 'Determina-

Letter to the Editor

tion of rare earth elements and yttrium in some uranium- and thorium-rich geological materials by inductively coupled plasma emission spectrometry” 4th titled ‘Chemical analysis – An instrumental approach’, Reference numbers 5–15 are cited at one place : Ref. Nos. 5–12 (all 8 references), are simply cut and pasted from their previous publication on UGTL’s¹⁵, Ref. No. 5 titled ‘Speciation analysis of chromium using cryptand ethers’, Ref. No. 6 titled ‘Speciation of Cr^{III} and Cr^{VI} in waters using immobilized moss and determination by ICP-MS and FAAS’, Ref. No. 7 titled ‘Preconcentrative separation of chromium(VI) species from chromium(III) by coprecipitation of its ethyle xanthate complex onto naphthalene’, Ref. No. 8 titled ‘On-line separation and preconcentration of chromium species in seawater’, Ref. No. 9 titled ‘On-line separation and preconcentration of chromium species in seawater’, Ref. No. 10 titled ‘Separation and speciation of Cr^{III} and Cr^{VI} with *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* immobilized on sepiolite and determination of both species in water by FAAS’, Ref. No. 11 titled ‘Uptake of chromium cations and anions by milled peat’, Ref. No. 12 cited as K. Chandrasekhar, N. S. Chary, C. T. Kamala, K. Rajni Supriya, T. Rameswar Rao, *Int. J. Environ. Stud.*, **5** (2002) 1, is incorrect and is absolutely wrong. This reference appears to be taken from a publication in *Talanta*, **65** (2005) 135–143, cited there as Ref. No. 28. A search was made through email to authors, journal search ‘*Int. J. Environ. Stud.*, **5** (2002) 1’ and through journal support system of Taylor & Francis Online Customer Services www.tandfonline.com Customer Services Survey and confirmed that we have unfortunately been unable to locate the article using the information supplied. Unfortunately the mentioned article (if referenced correctly) appears to be missing from our database. What is the necessity of citing such irrelevant reference? This publication is not a primary reference related to UGTL’s. Ref. No. 13 titled ‘Determination of rare earth elements in different geological matrices by ICP-AES after solid phase micro extraction on activated charcoal’, Ref. No. 14 titled ‘Removal of lead, cadmium and zinc by waste tea leaves’ Ref. No. 15 titled ‘Adsorption of divalent copper, zinc, cadmium and lead by waste tea and coffee’. There is no scientific discussion/comment on references cited in the manuscript and should be cited at appropriate places to support the statements. In my opin-

ion, only five references nos. 2, 4, 13, 14 and 15 are relevant and rest others are not related with the subject matter.

Such practices of organizing manuscript, citation of irrelevant publications, citation manipulation, citation of references without verifying original publications, copying and pasting of irrelevant references, without any significant improvements over existing methods, authors claim in absence of basic fundamental studies, fabrication of data, etc., constitutes research misconduct including plagiarism, citation manipulation, research integrity and is a gross violation of publication ethics. Since the above cited paper is duly reviewed by the publication committee of Atomic Minerals Directorate for Exploration and Research and approved by the competent authorities, it is the sole responsibility and involvement of the institution for encouraging researchers for such research and publication misconduct.

Recent article¹⁶ titled “Lessons from the recent publication scams” published in *Current Science*, Vol. 106, No. 5, 10 March, 2014, p. 649, is worth to be quoted here. In my opinion also, for the growth of science, it is important to teach ethics to researchers, and to keep a check on their work through individual institutions and departments. Such accountability can track individual scientific contributions, which would eventually, help one to stop or minimize scientific misconduct.

In view of the concerns expressed herein, authors are requested to kindly further document the reliability of their investigation.

References

1. Vijay Kumar, Sanjay Kumar, Naveen Kumar and P. N. Bangroo, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2013, **90**, 2147.
2. Nilanjana Das, R. Vimala and P. Karthika, *Indian J. Biotechnol.*, 2008, **7**, 159.
3. K. S. Geetha and S. L. Belagali, *IOSR Journal of Environmental Science, Toxicology and Food Technology (IOSR-JESTFT)*, 2013, **4**, 56.
4. Nilanjana Das and Devlina Das, *J. Rare Earths*, 2013, **31**, 933.
5. N. Tewari, P. Vasudevan and B. K. Guha, *Biochem. Eng. J.*, 2005, **23**, 185.
6. D. Kratochvil and B. Volesky, *Trends Biotechnol.*, 1998, **16**, 291.
7. R. R. Mohammed, *Arab. J. Sci. Eng.*, 2012, **37**, 1505.

8. A. Yoshita, J. L. Lu, J. H. Ye and Y. R. Liang, *African J. Biotechnol.*, 2009, **8**, 2212.
9. R. Lavecchia, A. Pugliese and A. Zuurro, *Chem. Eng. Trans.*, 2010, **19**, 73.
10. A. Zuurro and R. Lavecchia, *Am. J. Applied Sci.*, 2010, **7**, 153.
11. S. K. Bajpai and A. Jain, *Water SA*, 2010, **36**, 221.
12. www.google.com : [PDF] adsorption of heavy metals on activated charcoal prr.hec.gov.pk/Chapters/3053H-4.pdf and reference cited therein.
13. R. Qadeer, J. Hanif, M. Saleem and M. Afzal, *Colloid and Polymer Science*, 1993, **271**, 83 and reference cited therein.
14. Hisako Itoh, Hiromitsu Hachiya, Masashi Tsuchiya, Yasuo Suzuki and Yasukazu Asano, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Jpn.*, 1984, **57**, 1689.
15. Vijay Kumar, Satya Prakash and P. N. Bangroo, *Exploration and Research for Atomic Minerals*, 2009, **19**, 97.
16. A. A. Shah, *Current Science*, 2014, **106**, 649.